

LAKBAY-DIWA
Publishing

e-ISSN 3082-4397
p-ISSN 3082-5741

Volume I Issue VI

ECHOES *of* EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

OCTOBER 2025
MONTHLY ISSUE
NATIONAL

NATIONAL BOOK PUBLISHER IN THE PHILIPPINES
DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937
TIN 492-741-614
lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com
Butuan City, Philippines
+639543906965

Volume I Issue VI

ECHOES of EXPRESSION

A Creative Folio

Echoes of Expression

A Creative Folio

Volume I, Issue VI (October 2025), National Circulation

ISSN (Online) 3082-4397 ISSN (Print) 3082-5741

Published Online at www.lakbaydiwapublishing.com

Publisher: Lakbay-Diwa Publishing

DTI Business Reg. No. 6488937 / TIN 492-741-614

lakbaydiwapublishing@gmail.com

Butuan City, Philippines

+639543906965

AMYNA ZUBAYDAH P. MASORONG

Instructor III

Mindanao State University, Integrated Laboratory School

Marawi City, Philippines

[DOI 10.5281/zenodo.17411008](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17411008)

A New Life, Truly Mine

The path was long, a rugged trail,
Where fragile hopes begin to fade.
Each month, a sigh, a silent cry,
As whispering doubts filled my head.

Then a whisper, light and small,
A seed of joy starts to call.
A flutter of hope, a gentle plea,
Could this new life really be meant for me?

Now in my arms, a precious face,
A tiny miracle with love and grace.
I pray to believe that this path is true,
A love so pure, I vow to keep.